

DETECTING MENTAL DISORDERS IN SOCIAL MEDIA THROUGH EMOTIONAL PATTERNS THE CASE OF ANOREXIA

¹ M.JAYAKUMAR RAJU, PG STUDENT IN DEPT OF CSE IN SREE VAHINI INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, TIRUVURU, A.P, 521235.

² G.V.RAMANA, M.Tech,(Ph.D.), ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR IN DEPT OF CSE IN SREE VAHINI INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, TIRUVURU, A.P, 521235.

³ Dr. K.V. PANDURANGARAO Ph. D, HOD & PROFESSOR IN DEPT OF CSE IN SREE VAHINI INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, TIRUVURU, A.P, 521235.

ABSTRACT: Millions of people around the world are affected by one or more mental disorders that interfere in their thinking and behavior. A timely detection of these issues is challenging but crucial, since it could open the possibility to offer help to people before the illness gets worse. One alternative to accomplish this is to monitor how people express themselves that is for example what and how they write, or even a step further what emotions they express in their social media communications. In this study, we analyze two computational representations that aim to model the presence and changes of the emotions expressed by social media users. In our evaluation we use two recent public data sets for two important mental disorders: Depression and Anorexia. The obtained results suggest that the presence and variability of emotions, captured by the proposed representations, allow to highlight important information about social media users suffering from depression or anorexia. Furthermore, the fusion of both representations can boost the performance, equaling the best reported approach for depression and barely behind the top performer for anorexia by only 1%. Moreover, these representations open the possibility to add some interpretability to the results.

INTRODUCTION

A mental disorder causes different interferences in the thinking and behavior of the affected person [1]. These interferences could vary from mild to severe, and could result in an inability to live routines in daily life and ordinary demands [2]. Common mental disorders such as depression and anorexia affect millions of people around the world. They may be related to a single incident causing excessive stress on the person or by a series of different stressful events. It is also well known that mental disorders tend to increase in countries experiencing generalized violence or recurrent natural disasters. For example, in 2018 a study of mental disorders in Mexico revealed that 17% of its population has at least one mental disorder and one in four will suffer a mental disorder at least once in their life [3]. In another

vein, in the modern world, we take for granted that social life could be experienced either in the physical world or in a virtual world created by social media platforms like Face book, Twitter, Redd it, or similar platforms. This reality presents some challenges, but also great opportunities which, if properly addressed, could contribute to the understanding of what and how we communicate. In this regard, the goal of this study is to analyze, via the automatic identification of emotional patterns, social media documents 1 with the purpose of detecting the presence of signs of depression or anorexia in the population of that area [4]–[6]. Previous works have addressed the analysis of emotions of social media users by paying attention to their contrast and tone. They have mainly applied this analysis to predict users' age and gender as well as a range of sensitive personal attributes including sexual orientation, religion, political orientation [7], [8], income [9], and personality traits [10], [11]. According to these studies, the analysis of emotions in social media allows capturing important information related to users. This information presents an opportunity for us to extend the use of emotions in the detection of depression and anorexia in social media. Former studies focused on the detection of depression and anorexia have mainly considered linguistic and sentiment analysis [12]–[14]. Note that the use of sentiments, i.e. polarity, was the preamble for the later use of emotions for the same task [15]. This line of thought exposed the potential of using emotions as features, such as "anger", "surprise" or "joy", instead of linguistic features or general sentiments like positive and negative. In this direction, in our previous work [16], we introduced a novel representation that was built using information extracted from emotions lexicons combined with word embeddings as a way to represent the information contained in users' documents. Then, using a clustering algorithm, we created sub-groups of emotions , that conveniently we named as sub emotions.

LITERATURE SURVEY

An anti-phishing technique based on the visual similarity relies on the visual content of the web page received. Wilayat et al. [1] designed and developed a phish identification tool, called SpoofCatch, based on visual similarity. Using SpoofCatch, when the user first time visits a website, its login web page is identified and its screenshot is stored locally. When the user browse to the same website next time, the screenshot of its login page is compared with the locally stored ones. If a match is found with a local login page and the hosts of the login page received and previously visited are the same, the host is declared as genuine, otherwise, it is marked as phished. A promising strategy is offered in [15] for the visible distinction

among a suspected phishing website and the legal one. This strategy utilizes three web features that play a key role to decide whether the two pages are suspiciously identical. These characteristics are the fragments of the text and their layout, pictures inserted inside the page, including the general visual presentation of the website presented by the browser. An experimental test, using a data collection consisting of 41 real-world phishing sites besides their respective genuine destinations, displayed remarkable returns regarding the error rate.

HYBRID APPROACH FOR PHISHING DETECTION: A multidimensional spoofing and phishing detection feature has been modeled by the authors in [20]. This bi-step approach is primarily based on the deep learning algorithm. The authors proposed a Dynamic Category Decision Algorithm (DCDA) based on deep learning. More than a million malicious URLs were proceeded through this model. Results showed that their protection mechanism based on the proposed algorithm consumed less time to detect web-spoofing. A hybrid machine learning approach against phishing threats has been proposed by the authors in [21]. To build an effective model, five machine learning techniques have been used. The four-layered suggested model was then compared with the existing models after training on the necessary data set which included a significant number of URLs. Results demonstrated that the developed strategy was more efficient and effective. Kaur and Sharma [22] implemented the Repeated Incremental Pruning to Produce Error Reduction (RIPPER) [23] algorithm for malicious e-mail detection. An interesting feature of their implementation is that, after a phished URL is detected, it automatically generates a mail and sends it to the victim server. The email message includes the IP, location and contact info of the attacker server and blocks all the traffic coming from the server with malicious intentions. The authors in [24] have combined the machine learning and Resource Description Framework (RDF) to reduce false positives and enhance accuracy of their proposed model. Several machine learning approaches have been applied by the authors in [25] such as Linear Model (LM), Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF) and Neural Networks (NNs) on the test data to detect phishing and malicious sites.

ANTI-PHISHING MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES: Many researchers have designed effective, reliable and robust solutions for malicious URL detection based on machine learning techniques. Mao et al. [26] have described few attributes of web page that can be implemented to recognize phished URLs. They designed a logistic regression classifier and used it as a filter to distinguish phishing sites. It was observed that out of millions of URLs, approximately 777 phishing web sites were visited per day and almost

8.24% users were affected. In [14], the authors have evaluated nine techniques based on machine learning methodologies such as LR, RF, AdaBoost, SVM, NN, Naive Bayes, Bagging and Bayesian additive regression. The trained data set was based on 1500 phishing URLs and it was classified by machine learning. The authors in [27] applied a new tactic for phishing detection by designing a scalable classifier based on the machine learning. They trained their proposed model on the noisy data-sets. Their results showed that about 90% of the malicious URLs were detected using this approach. A PART-algorithm is used for spoof detection in [28] by the authors. They have implemented MAP-REDUCE [29] technique to boost-up the detection procedure. Jain et al. [30] carried out a comprehensive survey on existing techniques used for phishing detection across the globe. A Natural Language Processing (NLP) model based on machine learning.

EXISTING SYSTEM

Depression is a mental health disorder characterized by persistent loss of interest in activities, which can cause significant difficulties in everyday life. Studies focusing on the automatic detection of this disorder have used crowdsourcing as their main strategy to collect data from users who expressly have reported being diagnosed with clinical depression. Among these studies, the most popular approach considers words and word n-grams as features and employs traditional classification algorithms. The main idea is to capture the most frequent words used by individuals suffering from depression and compare them against the most frequent words used by healthy users. This approach suffers because there is usually a high overlap in the vocabulary of users with and without depression. Another group of works used a LIWC-based representation, aiming to represent users' posts by a set of psychologically meaningful categories like social relationships, thinking styles, or individual differences. These works have allowed a better characterization of the mental disorder conditions, nevertheless, they have only obtained moderately better results than using only the words. Recent works have considered ensemble approaches, which combine word and LIWC based representations with deep neural models such as LSTM and CNN networks. For example, in, the combination of these models with features like the frequencies of words, user-level linguistic metadata, and neural word embeddings offered the best-reported result in the eRisk- 2018 shared task on depression detection. These works show that in social media texts exist useful information to determine if a person suffers from depression, but the results are sometimes hard to interpret. This is an important limitation since these types of tools are

naturally aimed to support health professionals and not to take the final decisions. In the authors conduct studies to tackle this problem. They characterize users affected by mental disorders and provide methods for visualizing the data in order to provide useful insights to psychologists.

DISADVANTAGES OF EXISTING SYSTEM:

The system doesn't implement Converting text to sub-emotions sequences techniques.

2) The system doesn't implement emotion based detection of mental disorders.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed static and dynamic representations, named as BoSE and $_$ -BoSE respectively, are inspired in two hypotheses. The first one is that words assigned to coarse emotions in lexicons cannot capture subtle emotional differences, which in fact are what provide the most important insights into the mental health condition of users. For example, the lexicon associated with the anger emotion includes words such as furious, angry and upset that represent different degrees of anger, however, they are tagged with the same emotion. Thus, our proposal is to represent each user by a histogram of sub emotions, which are discovered by clustering the embedding's of words inside coarse emotions. The second hypothesis is that people with depression and anorexia tend to expose greater emotional variability than a healthy person. In this case, the idea is to represent each user by a set of statistical values that describe the frequency changes of the sub-emotions over time.

ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM:

The system further explores the BoSE representation and proposes a new representation based on sub-emotions that allow capturing the emotional variability of social media users over time.

2) The system proposes an approach to combine both static and dynamic representations using early and late fusion strategies to improve the detection of depression.

3) The system extends the use of these representations based on fine grained emotions for the task of anorexia detection and contrast the discovered emotional patterns with those obtained from the task of depression detection.

ALGORITHM

KNN Classifier Algorithm:

K-nearest neighbor method can be used for both regression and classification predictive problems. This method helps in interpret output, calculate time and predictive power. The Machine learning techniques are used in various fields. KNN is also one of the machine learning method. This is also called as method of sample-based learning. This will contain the data of past datasets and can be used while predicting the new datasets. This will apply function called as distance function like Manhattan or Euclidean distance. This can be used to compute distance from samples to all other training samples. It calculates the target value for new samples. The target vale will be the weighted sum of target values of the k nearest neighbours. The valve of K can be directly proportional to the prediction. Whenever the valve of K is small this indicates there is high variance and there is low bias. If the valve of the K is larger than this indicates that there is low variance and high bias. The main advantage of this KNN is it does not require any training or the optimization. This KNN uses data samples when predicting the new datasets. Hence it is having higher complexity and also more time consumption.

This work represents a review of K-NN technique for the early prediction of food recommendation. K-NN analysis is used for predicting the unknown parameter from the known parameters. In this work we are considering vitamins as input parameters which are the main parameters to be considered for a good food recommendation, although there are many other factors that can be considered [17]. The unknown value of vitamis can be predicted from the nearest known values of the nearest neighbors by calculation of Euclidean distance between them. Then we would be able to predict type of food for given vitamin parameters. To measure the distance between points in a feature space, various distance functions can be used, in which the Euclidean distance function is the most widely used one[18]. Let p and q are represented as feature vectors. To calculate the distance between p

and q, the Euclidean metric is generally used by if $a=(a_1, a_2)$ and $b=(b_1,b_2)$ then the distance is given

OUTPUT SCREENS

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Browse and Train 5 of Test Data Sets | View Trained and Tested Accuracy in Bar Chart | View Trained and Tested Accuracy Results | View Prediction Of Tweet Message Type
View Tweet Message Type Ratio | Download Trained Data Sets | View Tweet Type Ratio Results | View All Remote Users | Logout

Tweet Type Trained and Tested Results

Model Type	Accuracy
Naive Bayes	73.62668161434978
SVM	77.21412556053812
Logistic Regression	77.3822869955157
Decision Tree Classifier	69.22645739910314
SGD Classifier	77.83071748878923

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CONCLUSION

Users have become dependent on the online applications as they provide significant quality of service in many domains i.e., online banking, e-commerce, social connectivity, digital libraries, online health services, virtual education, digital marketing and multi-player gaming applications. Commonly, an authentication procedure is followed by the users for the creation of their online account to access the private web content. The security and privacy of users is at stake amid highly sophisticated web spoofing attacks. Several research and commercial tools have been developed to fight against web spoofing attacks but most of them appear with a few lapses. We have developed an optimized user-friendly browser plug-in dubbed as *Phish Catcher* for the smart disclosure of phishing attacks based on supervised machine learning. Contrary to the traditional approaches, our scheme offers to run the classification in the browser itself. It addresses the loopholes in the existing web applications by fixing the latency issues and improving the efficiency of the tool. The user interface of our plug-in is made simple for the better understanding of the user. When a user enters a phished URL, it displays a phishing alert on the screen and highlights the corresponding phishing features of that URL in a drop-down menu.

FUTURE SCOPE: The feature-set contains thirty features which are categorized into four groups where each group is acknowledged as a decision tree. Random forest classifier employs the aggregated outcome of the decision trees to identify the bogus and genuine login web pages. The data-set for testing and evaluation comprises of 400 malicious and 400 legitimate URLs. The criteria for testing and evaluation is based on a confusion matrix which enlists the true positives, true negatives, false positives and false negatives. Our plug-in displayed remarkable classification results with the precision and recall, both to be 98.5% and accuracy of 98.5%. Furthermore, the average latency of the plug-in was just 62.5 milliseconds which was measured by running it over forty phished URLs.

The feature set contains thirty features, though, the addition of more automated features might be a great idea to improve the overall performance. Some other discriminative classifiers such as SVM can also be implemented for the prediction of fake or real URL by training larger data-sets. Evaluation metrics may also be evolved by using different tools for a better performance analysis.

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